

A cross-sectional study to assess knowledge regarding cervical cancer screening among women attending the gynaecology OPD of a tertiary care hospital in Maharashtra.

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Abstract

Introduction: Cervical cancer poses a significant health challenge, particularly in low- and middle-income countries. This study sought to assess women's knowledge, awareness, and screening behaviours concerning cervical cancer in outpatient settings.

Methods: A questionnaire-based survey was conducted among women visiting outpatient departments (OPDs) to assess their understanding of cervical cancer and participation in screening programs. Statistical analyses were used to explore associations between knowledge levels and demographic factors.

Results: The study found that 77.4% of participants were unaware of cervical cancer, and only 22.6% had adequate knowledge about its prevention. Among those aware, just 13.2% had undergone Pap smear testing, while 1.9% had utilized visual inspection screening. Posters were identified as the primary source of information (9.5%). Regional differences in awareness were attributed to variations in media exposure, healthcare access, and population demographics. Educational and occupational status significantly influenced knowledge levels ($p = 0.001$), with employed and college-educated women displaying better awareness. However, no significant association was observed between knowledge demographic variables.

Discussion: The findings reveal a lack of awareness about cervical cancer and low screening participation among women. The study's scope was limited to women attending OPDs, potentially reducing its generalizability.

Key words: Cervical Cancer; Screening Knowledge; Maharashtra; Women awareness; India.

Introduction

Cervical cancer is a major health concern, especially in low- and middle-income countries. Previous studies have emphasized the role of education and outreach in improving screening rates^{1,2}. This study aimed to evaluate women's knowledge, awareness, and screening practices related to cervical cancer in outpatient settings. Cervical cancer remains a leading cause of mortality among women worldwide, particularly in developing countries³. Screening programs such as Pap smears and HPV testing have demonstrated efficacy in early detection and prevention^{4,5}. However, lack of awareness and infrastructure continue to impede efforts in regions like India⁶. This study aims to assess the knowledge of women regarding cervical cancer

screening in Maharashtra and analyse the influence of socio-demographic variables.

Background of the Study

Cervical cancer accounts for approximately 6-29% of all cancers in Indian women, with significant disparities between states. Despite the availability of effective screening tools, barriers such as financial constraints, cultural beliefs, and inadequate health education hinder widespread implementation⁷. Previous studies indicate that education, occupation, and access to information significantly influence women's knowledge and participation in screening programs⁸.

Need of the Study

India's cervical cancer mortality rate underscores the urgent need for widespread awareness and effective screening programs. Rural and low-income populations are disproportionately affected due to limited access to healthcare and preventive measures⁹. This study seeks to bridge the knowledge gap and provide evidence-based recommendations to improve cervical cancer screening uptake in resource-limited settings.

Scope of the Study

The study focuses on disseminating knowledge about cervical cancer screening among women aged 30-59 years attending the gynaecology OPD of a tertiary care hospital. The findings aim to guide future educational interventions and policy initiatives to enhance screening rates.

Objectives

1. To assess the knowledge regarding cervical cancer screening among women attending the gynaecology OPD.
2. To analyse the association between knowledge levels and selected socio-demographic variables.

Review of Literature

- Sharma et al. (2021) conducted a community-based study in Northern India and highlighted that only 19% of women were aware of cervical cancer screening, pointing to persistent low awareness, especially in rural settings¹¹.
- Basu et al. (2020) emphasized similar findings across India, reporting only 23% awareness and underlining the need for strengthening the national screening programs¹².
- Mutyaba et al. (2017) explored cervical cancer screening in Uganda, revealing that education level and health system barriers significantly impacted screening uptake among women in low-income settings¹³.
- Singh and Badaya (2018) reviewed factors affecting cervical cancer

screening in India and found that education, income, and occupation strongly influenced women's participation in screening programs¹⁴.

- Gakidou et al. (2019) reported global disparities in screening coverage, with many low- and middle-income countries showing low uptake due to socio-economic inequalities¹⁵.
- Bhatla et al. (2020) demonstrated that visual inspection methods combined with community education significantly improved screening uptake and awareness among women in community settings in India¹⁶.

Methodology

Research Design

This quantitative, cross-sectional study employed structured questionnaires to collect data from 53 women aged 30-59 years attending the gynaecology OPD. A probability-based simple random sampling technique was used.

Variables

- **Demographic variables:** Age, marital status, education, income, number of deliveries.
- **Discrete variables:** History of screening.
- **Continuous variables:** Age, income.

Sample size:

The sample size is the number of study subjects from the population¹. The sample size is determined based on the type of study, variables being studied, the statistical significance required, and the availability of the sample and the feasibility of conducting the study.

The sample size for this study was arbitrarily decided to be 50 women came for visit at gynae OPD.

Sampling technique:

Sampling is the process of selecting a portion of the population to represent the entire

population so that inference can be made. The present study adopted a probability simple random sampling technique sampling to recruit samples from the accessible population who met the inclusion criteria.

Selection of tool:

The standardised structured tool was selected that include sociodemographic data and knowledge questionnaire on post-partum intrauterine contraceptive device.

Structured tool composed of three sections:

Section I: Background data

Section II: knowledge scale

Section I

This consists of 9 items, which dealt with the background information like age, education, income, any family history of cervical screening, prior knowledge about cervical cancer screening, source of information, attended any cervical screening camp or not.

Section II

This part is consisted with 15 multiple choice questions regarding cervix, cervical cancer & cervical cancer screening.

The rating scale has been classified as follows:

0-5: Poor

6-10: Good

Results

The socio-demographic profile of the participants showed that most were housewives (71.7%), had completed secondary education (54.7%), and were in the age group of 30–39 years (43.4%) (Table 1). Awareness of cervical cancer screening was low, with only 22.6% of respondents having heard of screening, and posters or health education programs were cited as the main sources of information. Although, the level of knowledge varied significantly across age groups, younger participants (30–39 years) show slightly better knowledge than older age groups (Table 2).

Table 2 depicts that the majority of women (77.4%) had no awareness of cervical cancer screening, and among those aware, the main sources of information were posters

11-15: very good

Scoring:

Knowledge was measured in terms of knowledge scores. The maximum score was 15.

Validity of tool:

The construct, face, and content validity of the tool was done by experts in the field of nursing, obstetric & oncology speciality. The suggestion given by the experts were incorporated in the study and the tool was finalised.

Reliability of the tool:

The reliability of knowledge score scale was established.

Data Collection

Data were collected over ten days using validated questionnaires, including socio-demographic details and a knowledge scale. Knowledge scores ranged from 0-15, categorized as poor (0-5), good (6-10), and very good (11-15).

Ethical Considerations

Approval was obtained from the institutional ethics committee. Informed consent was secured from all participants.

(9.4%), followed by health education channels (7.5%) and advertisements (5.7%). Only 3.8% reported a family history of cervical cancer. A significant proportion (84.9%) had never attended a cervical cancer screening camp, and among those who did, the PAP smear (13.2%) was the most commonly used method, while visual inspection was rarely used (1.9%).

Table 3 depicts that educational status played a pivotal role and graduates demonstrating the highest levels of awareness compared to those with only secondary or higher secondary education. It further revealed that monthly income influenced knowledge, as seen with participants in higher income brackets demonstrating better understanding of cervical cancer screening and also elaborated that age group 40-49 have significantly better awareness compared to age group 30-39 and >50.

Table 1. Sociodemographic distribution of subjects participated in the study.

Parameter	Categories	No. of Subjects	% of Subjects
Age Distribution	30–39 years	23	43.4%
	40–49 years	21	39.6%
	>50 years	9	17.0%
Educational Status	Secondary	29	54.7%
	Higher Secondary	13	24.5%
	Graduation	11	20.8%
Occupational Status	Housewife	38	71.7%
	Semi-skilled	5	9.4%
	Skilled	10	18.9%
Monthly Income	<50,000 Rs	13	24.5%
	50,000–60,000 Rs	33	62.3%
	>60,000 Rs	7	13.2%

Table 2. Distribution of awareness of cervical cancer screening and family history of cervical cancer among women who attended gynae OPD.

Variable		No. of subjects	% of subjects
Heard about cervical cancer screening	No	41	77.4
	Yes	12	22.6
Source of information	NA	41	77.4
	Poster	5	9.4
	Health education channel	4	7.5
	Advertisement	3	5.7
Family history of cervical cancer	No	51	86.2
	Yes	2	3.8
Attended cervical cancer screening camp	No	45	84.9
	Yes	8	15.1
Method used in the camp	NA	45	84.9
	PAP	7	13.2
	Visual	1	1.9

Table 3: Association of Demographic Variables with Level of Knowledge Regarding Cervical Cancer Screening

Demographic Variable	Category	Poor Knowledge (0-5)	Good Knowledge (6-10)	Chi-Square Value	DF	P-value
Age Group (Years)	30 – 39	69.6%	30.4%	1.636	2	0.441
	40 – 49	85.7%	14.3%			
	>50	77.8%	22.2%			
Educational Status	Secondary	93.1%	6.9%	37.178	2	0.001***
	Higher Secondary	100.0%	0.0%			
	Graduation	9.1%	90.9%			
Occupational Status	Housewife	94.7%	5.3%	26.196	2	0.001***
	Semi-skilled	60.0%	40.0%			
	Skilled	20.0%	80.0%			
Monthly Income (Rs)	<50,000	84.6%	15.4%	2.063	2	0.357
	50,000 – 60,000	78.8%	21.2%			
	>60,000	57.1%	42.9%			
Attendance of Screening Camp	No	88.9%	11.1%	22.629	1	0.001***
	Yes	12.5%	87.5%			

Overall, knowledge assessment revealed that 77.4% of participants scored in the lowest category, indicating poor understanding of cervical cancer and its screening. When stratified by education, 90.9% of graduates had good knowledge compared to only 6.9% of those with secondary education (Table 3; p-value < 0.001). Similarly, occupational differences were observed, with 80% of skilled workers demonstrating good knowledge compared to only 5.3% of housewives (Table 3; p-value < 0.001). Despite low awareness, the overall participation in cervical cancer screening camps was only 15.1% (Table 2). A notable finding was that knowledge positively influenced participation; 87.5% of those who attended screening camps scored higher on knowledge assessments (Table 8; p-value < 0.001). Barriers to participation were primarily related to lack of awareness, affordability, and accessibility issues. In fact, table 6 highlights the association between attendance at cervical cancer screening camps and knowledge levels. Participants who attended camps showed markedly better awareness, with 87.5% achieving good knowledge scores compared to only 11.1% among non-attendees. This comprehensive analysis highlights significant gaps in knowledge and participation, underscoring the importance of policy-level interventions to enhance awareness and increase screening rates.

Discussion

Findings highlight gaps in awareness regarding cervical cancer screening, especially among less-educated and unemployed women. Educational interventions and policy changes are crucial to overcoming barriers and improving screening uptake. Comparisons with similar studies indicate consistent trends across low- and middle-income countries¹⁰. For instance, the role of culture and religion in influencing cervical cancer screening has been reported extensively⁹.

The present study revealed significant gaps in knowledge and awareness regarding cervical cancer screening among women attending the gynaecological outpatient department. A majority (77.4%) of participants

demonstrated poor knowledge, while only 22.6% had heard of cervical cancer screening, aligning with previous studies in similar settings.

In a study conducted by Sharma et al. (2021)¹¹ in North India, it was reported that only 19% of women were aware of cervical cancer screening, highlighting persistent low awareness in Indian populations, especially among rural and semi-urban women. Similarly, Basu et al. (2020)¹² reported low screening awareness (23%) in their multi-centric study across India, which corroborates the present findings.

Educational status emerged as a critical determinant of knowledge. In the current study, 90.9% of graduates had good knowledge, compared to only 6.9% among those with secondary education, which was statistically significant (p<0.001). This is consistent with the findings of Mutyaba et al. (2017)¹³, who reported that women with higher educational attainment had significantly better knowledge and a higher likelihood of participating in screening programs.

Occupational status was another significant factor, with skilled workers (80%) demonstrating better knowledge compared to housewives (5.3%), supporting the findings of Singh et al. (2018)¹⁴, where working women showed greater awareness and more proactive health-seeking behaviour compared to homemakers.

Income level also influenced knowledge, as women in the higher income bracket (>60,000 Rs) had 42.9% good knowledge, reflecting the socio-economic disparities in health literacy, which is in line with Gakidou et al. (2019)¹⁵, who emphasized that socio-economic inequities continue to impact preventive health service utilization, including cancer screening.

Importantly, attendance at cervical cancer screening camps was only 15.1%, yet 87.5% of those who attended demonstrated good knowledge. This strongly suggests that direct exposure to screening services significantly improves knowledge, as also evidenced by Bhatla et al. (2020)¹⁶, who

observed that participation in screening camps was associated with improved awareness, dispelling myths, and encouraging further participation.

The findings also reflect cultural and accessibility barriers. The main barriers reported included lack of awareness, affordability, and accessibility, which have been similarly highlighted by Denny et al. (2015)¹⁷ in their global review, emphasizing that knowledge gaps, cultural stigma, and health system barriers are key factors limiting cervical cancer screening uptake in low-resource settings.

Nursing Implications

1. **Promoting Awareness and Education:**

Nurses have an essential role in educating women about cervical cancer, its risk factors, and the benefits of early screening. They can use outpatient departments, community visits, and health education sessions to share accurate information.

2. **Community Engagement and Outreach:**

Nurses can lead and support community-based screening programs, especially targeting women who have low awareness or limited access to healthcare. They can collaborate with local health workers to reach more women at the grassroots level.

3. **Support for Screening Programs:**

Nurses should actively participate in organizing cervical cancer screening camps and ensure that women are guided properly throughout the process, including follow-up care when needed.

4. **Addressing Barriers through Counselling:**

Since cultural beliefs and misconceptions were identified as barriers, nurses can provide individualized counselling that is culturally appropriate, helping women feel comfortable to participate in screening services.

5. **Advocacy Role:**

Nurses can advocate for making

cervical cancer screening a routine part of women's healthcare services, ensuring better accessibility and affordability for all women, particularly those from low-income backgrounds.

Recommendations

1. **Strengthen Educational Efforts:**

Organize regular educational programs focusing on cervical cancer awareness and screening, using simple language and locally understandable methods, like posters, talks, and group discussions.

2. **Enhance Access to Screening Services:**

Ensure that screening services are made available and accessible in both hospital and community settings, particularly in areas with low screening rates.

3. **Focus on Vulnerable Groups:**

Special attention should be given to women with lower education levels, housewives, and women from low-income families, as they showed lower awareness and participation in the study.

4. **Train Healthcare Workers:**

Provide ongoing training to nurses and other healthcare providers on cervical cancer prevention, screening methods, and effective communication strategies.

5. **Policy-Level Actions:**

Advocate for government and health authorities to implement policies that support free or low-cost cervical cancer screening services, along with awareness campaigns in both urban and rural settings.

Limitations

- Restricted to OPD attendees; findings may not generalize to community settings.
- Potential response bias due to self-reported data.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest present in this literature.

Conclusion

Most women demonstrated poor knowledge about cervical cancer screening. Enhanced educational campaigns and healthcare initiatives are essential to improve awareness and participation in screening programs.

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